

EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH OF HYDRAULIC PARAMETERS OF PIPE NETWORKS WITH POLYETHYLENE AND GLASS-PLASTIC MATERIALS IN THE DRINKING WATER SUPPLY SYSTEM OF FERGANA CITY

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Abstract. The article examines the study of hydraulic parameters of pipes made of polyethylene and glass-plastic material in the field conditions. The hydraulic parameters of the water flow in the pipe were determined experimentally based on the method of the field research.

Key words: pipes made of polyethylene and glass-plastic material; hydraulic parameters.

Introduction. In recent years, as a result of laying and reconstruction of new pipes and replacement of used pipes in developed countries, the use of polyethylene and glass-plastic material pipes in drinking water supply systems occupies one of the main places. In light of the above the use of polyethylene and glass-plastic pipes for the purpose of providing drinking water to consumers in Fergana has been studied in this article.

The main part. A total of 636 km of pipes with a diameter of 110 mm to 1000 mm serve to provide drinking water to consumers in the city of Fergana. 95% (561 km) of existing 110-200 mm distribution pipes are made of polyethylene material, and 37% (17.1 km) of main pipes of 500 mm to 1000 mm size are made of polyethylene and glass-plastic material pipes. 81 percent (13.8 km) of the 17.1 km long trunk pipelines are made of polyethylene and 19 percent (3.3 km) of glass-plastic material pipes.

Hydraulic parameters of pipes made of polyethylene and glass-plastic material have been studied under the field conditions. Field experiments have been carried out using the following method: the experiments have been carried out on polyethylene and glass-plastic material pipes with dimensions of 500 mm, 800 mm and 1000 mm. For this purpose, calculated shears have been selected in the parts of the pipelines without side shafts, devices that create local resistances (shafts, valves, etc.). A line diagram of selected design shifts is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Line diagram of the part of the polyethylene and glass-plastic pipe system where field experiments have been conducted.

Field research has been carried out using modern equipment:

Figure 2. General view of the AFT-2000H portable device with a laser, which makes it possible to measure the consumption of water flow in pressure pipes in the drinking water supply system.

Field research have been carried out in March, May and November 2023. The pipeline networks where the field studies have been conducted are presented in Figure 1. Estimated shears were determined at the points of connection of pipes (in wells where shut-off valves are located). In order to

determine experimentally the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in the pipeline, based on the method of field research, it was carried out in the parts of the pipeline network where there are no local resistances (shut-off valves, bends, tees, etc.). Field studies (2-2) - (4-4) on a pipe with 430 p/m polyethylene material with a size of 500 mm between calculated shears, (5-5) (6-6) on a 647 p/m polyethylene pipe with a size of 600 mm between calculated shears (6-6) in a material pipe, (3-3) (4-4) in a 725 p/m glass-plastic material pipe with a size of 1000 mm between the calculated shears, and (4-4)-(5-5) with a size of 1000 mm between the calculated shears in a 975 p/m glass-plastic material pipe, between calculated shears (5-5)-(7-7) in a 1100 p/m glass-plastic material pipe with a size of 800 mm and (7-7)-(8-8) was performed on glass-plastic material pipes 504 p/m long with a size of 600 mm between calculated shears. 5 series of experiments have been performed in each tube.

The pipelines, which underwent field research, were reconstructed and put into operation in 2022. It was found that the pipes had been new after visual inspection of the field research conducted pipes and according to the opinion of the experts of the operating organization. This situation provides a good opportunity to study the hydraulic parameters of water flow in pipes.

As a result of conducting field research, the hydraulic parameters of water flow in pipes made of polyethylene and glass-plastic material with a size of 500 mm, 800 mm and 1000 mm have been determined.

The results of field studies are presented in the following tables and figures.

Table 1

The results of the experiment conducted on a 500 mm polyethylene pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(2-2)-(4-4)	0,009	0,5	0,20	1,57	0,13	0,11	88,66

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u^2	λ
(2-2)-(4-4)	0,5	4511	430	1000	1,12	1,2544	0,008363

Figure 3. Diagram of experimental values of the geometric dimensions of the pipe with polyethylene material and the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it between the calculated shears (2-2) and (4-4)

Table 2

The results of the experiment conducted on a 600 mm polyethylene pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(5-5)-(6-6)	0,0096	0,6	0,28	1,88	0,15	0,11	84,91

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$			L	ρ	u	u ²	λ
(5-5)-(6-6)	0,6	4119	643	1000	1,12	1,2544		0,00609	

Figure4. Diagram of the geometric dimensions of the polyethylene material pipe between the calculated shears (5-5) and (6-6) and the experimental values of the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it

Table 3

The results of the experiment conducted on a 600 mm polyethylene pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(9-9)-(10-10)	0,0093	0,6	0,28	1,88	0,15	0,11	87,57

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u2	λ
(9-9)-(10-10)	0,6	4511	1300	1000	1,1	1,21	0,00344

Figure 5. Diagram of the geometric dimensions of the polyethylene material pipe and the experimental values of the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it between the calculated shears (9-9) and (10-10)

Table 4

The results of the experiment conducted on a polyethylene pipe of 800 mm size

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(3-3)-(9-9)	0,0097	0,8	0,50	2,51	0,20	0,11	86,69

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u2	λ
(3-3)-(9-9)	0,8	4511	1300	1000	1,22	1,48	0,0037

Figure 6. Diagram of experimental values of the geometric dimensions of the polyethylene material pipe and the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it between the calculated shears (3-3) and (9-9)

Table 5

The results of the experiment conducted on a 600 mm glass-plastic material pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(7-7)-(8-8)	0,012	0,6	0,28	1,88	0,15	0,10	68,36

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u2	λ
(7-7)-(8-8)	0,6	6668	500	1000	1,32	1,74	0,0091

Figure 7. Diagram of the geometric dimensions of the glass-plastic material pipe between the computational shears (7-7) and (8-8) and the experimental values of the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it

Table 6

The results of an experiment conducted on a 800 mm glass-plastic material pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(5-5)-(7-7)	0,011	0,8	0,50	2,51	0,20	0,11	76,71

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u2	λ
(5-5)-(7-7)	0,8	6668	1100	1000	1,23	1,51	0,0064

Figure 8. Diagram of the geometric dimensions of the glass-plastic material pipe and the experimental values of the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it between the calculated shears (5-5) and (7-7)

Table 7

The results of the experiment conducted on a 1000 mm glass-plastic material pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(4-4)-(5-5)	0,01	1	0,79	3,14	0,25	0,11	86,19

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u2	λ
(4-4)-(5-5)	1	5884	975	1000	1,24	1,54	0,0079

Figure 10. Diagram of the geometric dimensions of the glass-plastic material pipe between the calculated shears (4-4) and (5-5) and the experimental values of the hydraulic parameters of the water flow in it

Table 8

The results of the experiment conducted on a 1000 mm glass-plastic material pipe

Sashes	n	d	ω	X	R	y	C
(3-3)-(4-4)	0,01	1	0,79	3,14	0,25	0,11	86,19

Sashes	d	$\Delta\rho$	L	ρ	u	u2	λ
(3-3)-(4-4)	1	6374	1300	1000	1,14	1,3	0,0075

Conclusion. 1. The hydraulic parameters of the water flow in water networks made of polyethylene and glass-plastic materials 1.7 km long measuring 500 mm to 1000 mm in the drinking water supply system of the city of Fergana have been experimentally studied.

2. The Shezi coefficient has been experimentally studied in water flow in water networks made of polyethylene and glass-plastic materials 1.2 km long measuring from 500 mm to 1000 mm. The Shezi coefficient has been determined experimentally at different values (0.009; 0.0093; 0.0097; 0.010; 0.011) of the roughness coefficient of the inner surface of water pipes made of polyethylene and glass-plastic materials and at different parameters of the hydraulic radius.

3. Experimental values of the coefficient of hydraulic resistance have been found in water flow in water networks made of polyethylene and glass-plastic materials 0.5 km long measuring from 500 mm to 1000 mm.

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